

see table) were resistant to the chemical when compared with the most susceptible population (C), and using a resistance ratio of 5 as the demarcation.

No apparent relationship between susceptibility to this compound and the cholinesterase activity of the populations could be found, although the most resistant population (E) showed the lowest cholinesterase activity, and the least sensitivity to vamidothion. When populations E and B were compared, a resistance ratio of about 6 was found associated with an I_{50} ratio of about 5. The results indicate that reduced cholinesterase activity and a change of

Vamidothion susceptibility, cholinesterase activity, and sensitivity of rice green leafhoppers in central Taiwan.

Population	Location	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)	Resistance ratio	Cholinesterase	
				Activity (µmol/min)	I ₅₀ M
A	Shu-wang	10.57	8.7:1	0.069	4.40×10^{-4}
B	Wu-fu	5.53	4.5:1	0.093	2.70×10^{-4}
C	Hsia-tien	1.22	1.0:1	0.054	3.60×10^{-4}
D	Nay-hsin	4.07	3.3:1	0.057	5.00×10^{-4}
E	Lu-tsun	32.10	26.3:1	0.050	1.44×10^{-3}

the target site sensitivity could play a considerable role in vamidothion resistance in GLH. Electrophoretic

studies revealed qualitative differences in esterase zymograms among the populations. ■

Effect of selected insecticides on striped stem borer eggs

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Eggs of the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis* in the blackhead stage were treated with candidate insecticides at 0.04% concentration. Before treatment, each egg mass was examined under the microscope to determine the initial number of eggs per mass. Three egg masses were dipped in insecticide solutions for 5 minutes then transferred to a petri dish with moistened filter paper

Effect of selected insecticides on eggs of the striped stem borer. IRRRI 1979.

Insecticide	Formulation	Eggs (initial no.)	Unhatched eggs (no.)	Ovicidal ^a activity (%)
Methyl parathion	50 EC	661	622	92.9
Carbofuran	12 F	596	593	99.4
Methomyl	90 WP	619	600	96.5
Triazophos	40 EC	656	588	89.1
Control		586	163	26.4

^a Av of 4 replications, each containing 3 egg masses.

and kept in an insectary for 48 hours. The eggs were counted again to determine the number that were unhatched. Larvae that emerged and died alter hatching

were considered hatched. Each treatment was replicated four times. The table shows the results. ■

Soil and crop management

Preference for ammonium sulfate as first topdressing in lev method of rice cultivation

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Farmers in Karchhana Tahsil, Allahabad district, commonly direct-seed rice with little field preparation after the onset of the monsoon. To control weeds, they then plow the crop with a deshia plow and plank it under flooded conditions

when plants are about 1 month old or 15–21 cm tall. The practice is locally called *lev*. Progressive farmers in the area claim that ammonium sulfate is superior to urea as the first topdressing in that rice-cultivation method. An experiment in farmers' fields was conducted to investigate the claim.

Sixteen farmers' fields, selected during 1978 kharif, were prepared with two cross plows. No basal fertilizers were applied. The variety Saket 4 was broadcast seeded at 100 kg seed/ha in the first week of July. Five weeks after

sowing the plots were plowed twice with a deshia plow and planked under flooded conditions. In the first eight plots, ammonium sulfate was topdressed immediately after plowing; in the other eight plots, urea was topdressed a week after plowing. Both fertilizer treatments were at 40 kg N/ha. The second topdressing was applied uniformly in all plots about 10 weeks after sowing with 30 kg N/ha as urea.

Visual observations 2 weeks after the first topdressing showed that weed re-establishment, weed density, and weed

growth were less in the plots that received ammonium sulfate than in the plots that received urea. Ammonium sulfate also helped decompose weeds. Urea applied a week after crop plowing did not

influence weed decomposition, so most of the weeds re-established. Grain yields were also remarkably increased. Average grain yield was 3.26 t/ha for the ammonium sulfate treatment, and

2.4 t/ha for urea. Since no additional input costs are involved, extension agencies may consider suggesting the method to farmers. ■

Influence of soil moisture regime on iron and manganese release in soil and on the growth of upland rice

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A pot experiment, conducted on Vertic Ustropepts (medium black clay: pH 8.5; CaCO₃, 6.0%; and organic carbon, 0.5%)

in the 1977 rainy season, studied the influence of soil saturation and submergence for 10 and 20 days before sowing on the supply of iron and manganese in the soil and on the dry matter yield of upland rice. The variety used was Karjat 184.

The iron and manganese supply in the soil increased with the duration of soil saturation or submergence (see table). The increase may have been caused by

moderately reduced soil conditions that resulted from soil saturation or submergence before sowing (Eh values decreased from 501 mV to 369 mV and pH decreased from 8.6 to 7.6). Iron and manganese contents in the soil were higher after submergence for 10 or 20 days than after soil saturation. The dry-matter yield increased — probably because of the higher supply of iron and manganese. ■

Iron and manganese contents in soil and dry matter yield of rice as influenced by soil moisture regimes before sowing. Mean of 5 replications. Maharashtra, India

Soil water treatment before sowing	Iron content (ppm)		Manganese content (ppm)		Dry matter yield of rice at harvest (g/5 plants per pot)
	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period 10 or 20 days)	Initial (immediately after soil water treatment)	Final (at the end of soil water treatment period)	
Soil saturation, 10 days	2.4	2.6	0.7	1.0	5.3
Soil submergence, 10 days	2.6	3.2	0.7	1.3	7.6
Soil saturation, 20 days	2.4	3.6	0.7	1.2	7.5
Soil submergence, 20 days	2.6	4.1	0.7	2.1	8.9
Control (dry soil)	1.2	1.2	0.7	0.7	5.2

A simple test for available zinc and copper in wetland rice soils

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Zinc deficiency is a widespread nutritional disorder of wetland rice. It occurs on alkali, calcareous, poorly drained mineral, and peat soils. Copper deficiency limits rice yields on peat soils and also, perhaps, on other zinc-deficient soils. The need for simple, rapid, and reliable method for estimating zinc and copper in soils used for wetland rice is pressing.

Because the widely used DTPA and EDTA methods consume too much time and chemicals, 0.1 N HCl and 0.05 N HCl as extractants for available zinc and copper were compared with DTPA and

EDTA in a laboratory and greenhouse study of 32 soils covering a wide range of pH and organic matter content.

The 0.1 N HCl method consisted of shaking 2 g air-dry soil with 20 ml 0.1 N HCl for 5 minutes. The 0.05 N HCl method used 10 g air-dry soil, 20 ml 0.05 N HCl, and 5 minutes shaking. The extracts were filtered and zinc and copper determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry, along with the DTPA and EDTA extracts obtained by shaking for 2 hours and 30 minutes, respectively. Rice plants grown on the flooded soils were wet-ashed and the concentrations of zinc and copper measured.

The 0.05 N HCl method gave the best correlation between extractable zinc and copper and their concentration in the plant:

Method	Concn of element in extract vs concn in plant	
	Zn	Cu
ESDTA-(NH ₄) ₂ CO ₃	.43**	.28ns
DTPA/TEA	.31 ns	.20ns
0.1 N HCl	.55**	.64**
0.05 N HCl	.88**	.74**

On 13 of the 16 soils that contained less than 1 ppm Zn extractable with 0.05 N HCl, plants showed zinc deficiency symptoms or contained < 27 ppm zinc. Although no copper deficiency symptoms were recognized, plants growing on 13 of 15 soils with < 0.1 ppm Cu by the 0.05 N HCl method contained < 5 ppm copper.

Available zinc (0.05 N HCl) correlated highly with available copper (0.05 N HCl) with $r = .58^{**}$. So did plant zinc and